

A trapped generation: Letters from Sent-down Youth in the Chinese Cultural Revolution (1966-67)¹

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Abstract

In the wake of 1960s student movements all around the globe, Chinese youth initiated a country-wide revolution against the “capitalist” elements in the ruling communist party and in Chinese culture. In 1968, as the movement caused massive chaos in the country, Chairman Mao Zedong called for the youth to resettle in rural area in China to restore the order in cities. This is referred to as the “Up to the Mountains and Down to the Countryside Movement,” of “educated youth,” who graduated from middle schools or high schools. Estimated 17 millions of young people went to the rural villages, border areas, military farms, and outskirts of cities during the sent-down movement which formed a special generation of mass displacement.

It is acknowledged by many, though certainly not all, historians that these youth suffered severely under hard labour, food shortage, and separation with families, etc. While historical research on the educated youth is expanding their depth and scope, many are based on secondary sources, fictions, and official reports, which are further away from the real fabric of the lives of the sent-down youth. Thus, this article aims to diversify the sources of historical evidence by adding private letters to the discussion. During the movement, letters were the main way for rusticated youths to communicate with their friends and families, and loved ones. Letter writing became a ritual-like routine that allowed spontaneous and intimate expression of emotions and thoughts, which were often not found in official documents and

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newspapers. Unlike memoirs and scar literature, it provides a perceptive that is undistorted by hindsight. This article carefully examines a collection of letters written by an individual male sent-down youth during 1968-75 as a case study. Through his account of the ups and downs in a farm, his laughter and tears, his hard labour in the field and his romantic encounters, this article produces a historical-analytical bottom-up narrative. With the lens of social and cultural history, I would trace the movements of the sent-down students and their change in emotions and beliefs throughout the period.

Upon in-depth analysis, one finds that it was possible for educated youth to spend their first flush of adulthood in farms living a life that solely depended on the Party ideology in their behavior and mentality. The letters are full of down-to-earth details in daily-life, that one perhaps find the educated youth not as distant to us as we thought. They remind us that another vast dislocation project with tragic consequences is not impossible and unacceptable under the regime of the CPC (Communist Party of China) with ordinary teenagers who can engage in state mobilizations without a thought on its shortcomings and dangers. It is important for us contemporaries to understand the sent-down generation as they were, so as to reflect on the nature, impact, and replicability of the massive rustication project.

Introduction

A typical day for an educated youth, Wang Shu, in China in the 1970s during the send-down movement consisted of mowing in the field, dragging political meetings and five hours of sleep. For us contemporaries, his days seem to be harsh and daunting. Many of his fellows, in later first-person narrations, voiced their boredom, sufferings, and traumas in the years in the rural area. But what did Wang think about it? The youth actually found it delightful and rewarding! To the perplexity of many, how did Wang, a member of the “lost generation” (*shiluo de yidai*) going through rustication,² act out the meaning of his life in the remote youth military farm with satisfaction and self-motivation?

The “lost generation” is also identified as the “educated youth” (*zhishi qingnian* or *zhiqing* in short), are students who were in or graduated from elementary, middle, or high school and were sent to the countryside under the campaign of *Up to Mountain Down to Countryside Movement* (*shangshan xiaxiang*, also translated as the sent-down campaign) in 1968, two years after the beginning of the Cultural Revolution. Before 1968, the targets of the sent-down program were mainly jobless city dwellers. In this period, approximately one million individuals were sent down.³ Amid the frenzy of the Cultural Revolution and the Red Guard movement in 1968, the Maoist leadership had to deal with the troubles caused by the Red Guards. As the radical and anarchical Red Guards stormed administrations and institutions, the Party leaders realized the necessity of restoring social order and production efficiency, through channelling their idealism and activism to elsewhere – the countryside. Subsequently, since 1968, relocation to the countryside was compulsory for urban youths who had finished schooling. The campaign soon

² For the terminology, see Michel Bonnin, “The “Lost Generation”: Its Definition and Its Role in Today's Chinese Elite Politics,” *China in Transition* 73 (Spring 2006): 249.

³ Thomas P. Bernstein, *Up to the Mountains and Down to the Villages: the Transfer of Youth from Urban to Rural China*, (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1977), 24.

became coercive, as there was resistance to it when the reality of rural lives was exposed in the cities. Between 1968 and 1980, about 17 million Chinese urban youth, accounting for about one-third of the population in the age group, were rusticated, and many stayed there for more than 10 years.⁴ It became a massive relocation project of youth from areas with a higher living standard to the areas with a lower one, from the industrialized to the nature-dominant environment. The CCP leaders aimed to, via population relocation, solve urban unemployment, restore social orders, reprogram the education system, and modernize the rural areas and frontiers.

The pivotal, lasting impact on the sent-down generation received both modern Chinese and international scholars' attention. Aside from the typical approach of analysing the Sent-down movement based on top-down politics, a careful look on at individuals' lives also helps to recast the meaning and lessons of the Cultural Revolution. In this essay, I am trying to write a history "from below" of the sent-down movement based on a collection of private letters the educated youth sent to his family. These letters by a young male, Wang Shu, reflect the inner world of the educated youth in first-person narrative with a combination of subjective expression and objective observation. The letters may provide insights into the rustication program from a micro-perspective and complement mainstream historical narratives.

In China, the Up to the Mountain and Down to the Countryside movement has been a sensitive topic. The state has been trying to avoid accusations about the coercive nature of the movement and their responsibility for the sufferings the youth faced thereat. Therefore, there has been

⁴ Liu Xiaomen, *Zhongguo zhiqingshi: Dachao* 中國知青史：大潮 (1953–1968) [History of *Zhiqing* in China: the spring tide (1966–1980)] (Beijing: China Social Sciences Press, 1998), 863.

limited discussion on the topic in Chinese academia, and researchers have heavily relied on official propaganda as evidence.⁵

Outside the country, foreign scholars have also expressed interest in the topic. Like many historical investigations in the initial stage, a top-down approach was first used, focusing on Mao's motivation for launching the rustication.⁶ Historians later turned more to the sufferings of the youth in the countryside with a bottom-up approach with the increasing availability of autobiographies and other sources in English and the growing community of Chinese diaspora.⁷ The so-called "scar literature" (*shanghen wenxu*) and educated youth literature (*zhiqing wenxue*) became a publishing phenomenon and the major sources of reference on the topic.⁸ They illustrate the cruelty of the sent down movement in the Cultural Revolution, and provide historians with an alternative source outside the party's statement.

However, reliance on "scar literature," autobiographies and memoirs as sources prompted other problems. For one, they have been often referenced in the main text without the specification of their fictional character.⁹ In many of the historians' work on the sent-down movement, their

⁵ Chen Yi, Fan Ziying, Gu Xiaomin, Zhou LiAn, "Arrival of Young Talent: The Send-Down Movement and Rural Education in China," *American Economic Review* 110.11 (2020): 3393-3430.

Gu H. ed., *Zhongguo Zhishi Qingnian Shangshan Xiexiang Chimo* 中國知識青年上山下鄉始末 [The whole story of *Zhiqing* UMD in China], (Beijing: China Procuratorial Press, 1997).

⁶ For example, Stuart R Schram ed., *Authority, Participation and Cultural Change in China: Essays by a European Study Group*, (Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 1973).

Gordon D. White, "The politics of hsia-hsiang youth," *China Quarter*, (1974): 491.

⁷ Michel Bonnin and Horko Krystyna, *The lost generation: The rustication of China's educated youth (1968–1980)*, (Shatin: The Chinese University of Hong Kong Press, 2013).

⁸ Ou Nianzhong and Liang Yongkang ed., Laura Maynard trans., *Mao's Lost Children: Stories of the Rusticated Youth of China's Cultural Revolution*, (Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2015).

Pan Yihong, *Tempered in the Revolutionary Furnace: China's Youth in the Rustication Movement*, (Lanham, Md.: Lexington, 2002).

⁹ Judith Shapiro, *Mao's war against nature: Politics and the environment in revolutionary China*, (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001.)

analytical distinction of fictional sources from the non-fictional ones has been obscure. Since they provide plausible accounts and explanations, they seduce readers to take them as reliable history. As a result, the literary devices and imaginary scenes from those fictions have exaggerated or distorted the actual historical incident, and historians accordingly have constructed a narrative further away from historicity. Aside from fiction, memoirs are employed by many historians without being cautious of the bias of the source. Memoirs are flawed with human memories that are largely influenced by hindsight social collective construction and imposition, in addition to the natural memory lost.¹⁰ Especially in the People's Republic of China (PRC), where the government actively propagandized and pressed one prominent dominative official narrative on the public, recollection is even further from the historic truth. In these personal narratives, what happened on the ground is hard to distinguish from self-justification and victimization. The former educated youth often fit their accounts into two opposing frames –glorification and victimization.¹¹ On the one hand, they exhibited nostalgia for the freedom and achievements in the rural area, largely as a resistance against the rapid socio-economic shift in China since the 1990s. On the other hand, the narrators portrayed themselves as victims of the sent-down movement by emphasizing their sufferings and misfortunes, and labelling the days spent in the rural areas as “the lost years.” While many historians are aware of the limitations of relying on fiction and memoirs in reconstructing a more truthful rustication process, they cannot assemble their research in other ways due to the lack of diversity of sources. With the censorship of non-official publications, the sensitivity of

¹⁰ For more on the role of memoirs, and the memory in general, see: ”Xu Zidong, *Weile wangque de jiti jiyi: jiedu 50 pian wenge xiaoshuo* 為了忘卻的集體記憶：解讀五十篇文革小說 [For the forgotten collective memory: an analysis of 50 samples of Cultural Revolution fiction] (Beijing: Sanlian shudian, 2000).

Peter Zarrow, “Meanings of China’s Cultural Revolution: memoirs of exile,” *Positions* 7, 1(1999): 165-191.

¹¹ Michel Bonnin, “Restricted, distorted but alive: The memory of the “lost generation” of Chinese educated youth,” *The China Quarterly* 227 (2016): 752-772.

Jiang Yarong and David Ashley, *Mao's children in the new China: voices from the Red Guard generation* (London: Psychology Press, 2000).

the subject, and limited access to archives, historians on the Cultural Revolution are in a disadvantageous position in collecting sources compared to their colleagues on other topics.

To write a history less confined by hindsight, presentism, self-interest, and memory flaws, historians may consider using private letters as evidence. As primary sources, they expand our knowledge on a historical topic with its random, arbitrary and spontaneous expressions. It bears less burden of judgement as a non-retrospective narration and does not illustrate a planned story plot. As a first-hand non-anonymous source, it dates the events and narrates them when memories are fresh, emotions linger. It represents less of a collective consensus of a historical event, but a more personal take on and candid picture of the era.

Letters are a particularly helpful source for history research around the Cultural Revolution, as they are less infiltrated with official dogmas. In an era where the authorities stressed collectivism and the denial of self, these personal accounts show individuality amid the repression of personal life.¹² Under intense state surveillance and censorship, diaries were even written as showpieces. But letters were less subjected to official inspection, as processing a huge number of letters was troublesome and timely, and it was hard to seal the envelope after opening them.¹³ Thus, the letter-writers tend to express more private and socially or legally forbidden thoughts. In the countryside, letter writing and reading became a habit, a sacred ritual

¹² Bonnin, "Restricted, Distorted but Alive," 755-756.

¹³ This is not to say that letters from and to the sent-down youth were not subject to inspection. There was certainly no respect for individual privacy –the officials could open any letters or packages they found suspicious. But based on the multiple collections of letters I have read, either published or posted on online anonymously, those letters contained more or less some forbidden or politically incorrect messages, thus implying the letter-writers mostly did not expect their letters to be seen by third party. In a letter from a sent-down cadre, the letter-writer said he "doesn't need to think about what kind of words I should use" when he was writing to his wife. See bibliography for other collections of letters.

that many educated youth were committed to regularly. It was a moment to connect with their loved ones, as well as a medium for individual expression and reflection¹⁴

While letters do serve the personal interest of the writers, who undoubtedly conceal some facts while exaggerating others, it is the subjectivity that matters here. It does not always authentically reflect historical moments, but instead values, attitudes, beliefs, feelings of the participants of the historical moments, which will be more valuable when reinforced with other readings. A close reading of an individual case does not produce a comprehensive historical narrative, nor does it spill out all cause-and-effect of the historical event, but it provides valuable insights and emotional dimensions of individuals. This letter collection particularly has a wider importance in the research of educated youth, for it seems to be a rare survival of its kind, and likely the story of Wang and his parents' response are not unique. The value of Wang's letters lays in their richness in the information of his inner world and feelings.

Wang Shu: a “living Lei Feng”?

I acquired Wang Shu's letters on a Chinese second-hand books trading platform. Among the countless items of letters and writings of the educated youth of different qualities, I found Wang's collection to be the most comprehensive and legible. His letters, written between 1968 and 1975, address his parents.

¹⁴ Yang Guobin, *The Red Guard Generation and Political Activism in China*, (New York: Columbia University Press, 2016,) 120-124.

According to his letters,¹⁵ the young fellow was born on November 2, 1948, one year before the Communist Party took over the whole country and established its regime. Twenty years later, Wang became one of the millions of educated youths who were exiled to the countryside in 1968. His more-than-common given name, *Shu*, which means tree, also designated his character - lively and sturdily. From a family of six in Harbin, Heilongjiang, Wang was the opposite of a stereotypical buff and assertive North-eastern Chinese. The skinny young man with a self-disciplined, polite, and versatile personality, wore a pair of glasses and a watch. From his writings that have barely any literary errors, one can easily see that he was very well educated. Wang left his home city to the Greater Khingan Range (or Da Hinggan Range) in Inner Mongolia, the most northern part of China, while his elder sister and younger brother were also sent to different parts of the country for labour. Wang's father – a serious, stern man – was a cadre and was occasionally sent to different places to work, leaving his frail mother and younger sister at home. Wang wrote down his day-to-day life on those A4 single-lined, grid or plain white papers in neat handwriting with an ink pen, addressed to his beloved family. He always greeted his parents with enthusiasm in the beginning, and signed and dated the letters at the bottom of the papers.

Wang's experience in the rural area is not a particularly exciting one. Unlike many best-selling educated youth fictions or memoirs, Wang's writings recorded no rebellions, no killing, no sneaky underground activities. Of course, it does not mean that he did not witness any, nor those did not happen. It is in fact the opposite – historians now have more evidence of how realities of the rustication differed from the official portrayal – idyllic countryside where educated youth

¹⁵ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu [Little Shu's family letters]. Acquired on January, 2020 through Kongfuzi jiushuwang, <https://www.kongfz.com/>. There are 64 letters in the collection, all in good condition. The letters were all written in simplified Chinese. They are two to three pages long. They are usually signed with the date, but some just with the month or the year. Two short letters come without any indication of date.

worked hand-in-hand with peasants and learned from each other.¹⁶ For one, the youth encountered immense difficulties, ranging from the lack of food, poor living conditions, sickness, unbearable labour, to isolation, conflicts with local peasants, and sexual assaults.¹⁷ Many memoirs recorded the lingering traumas. For another, underground literature, music, and art flourished when the youth first experienced freedom outside the tight supervision of state organizations in the cities.¹⁸ Some copied Russian literature by hand, while some assembled their own radios. It is beyond doubt that the experience of the sent-down youth varied greatly and mostly did not conform with official intentions and narratives.

It is under this historical context that Wang's experience became interesting – interestingly boring. He fits comfortably into the state narrative of an ideal educated youth – passionate about revolutions and political education, very hardworking, devoting the heart and soul to national modernization. Wang saw himself, just as Mao would have wanted, as a revolutionary successor.

Wang's generation grew up in the “New China,” in which they received political socialization and education that centred around the glorification of Mao, loyalty to the Party, and patriotism.¹⁹ A major education method was propagating “heroic models” (*yingmo*). The state constructed these model soldiers, model workers, model peasants and model youth to be celebrities, and their accomplishments and qualities served as the ideological and moral guidance for the

¹⁶ Bonnin and Horko, *The Lost Generation*, 453.

¹⁷ “Material Difficulties and Low Morale” in Bonnin and Horko, *The Lost Generation*, 235-326.

¹⁸ “The Second Society,” in Frank Dikötter, *The Cultural Revolution: A People's History, 1962–1976*, (Bloomsbury Publishing USA, 2016), 285-300.

¹⁹ Chen Yixin, “Lost in revolution and reform: The socioeconomic pains of China's red guards generation, 1966–1996,” *Journal of Contemporary China* 8.21 (1999): 222.

nation.²⁰ Articles in the *People's Daily*, movies, posters, exhibitions, songs, in addition to work-unit study sessions and school text tasks, were created around them. Among the heroic models, Lei Feng (1940-1962) has been the most widely known figure since the 1960s till the present day. His diary was published and became a must-have for every household.²¹ Most young people in the Red Guard generation accepted the Lei Feng spirit without question at an early age.²² Lei Feng, a PLA soldier who died protecting the public properties in 1962, was hugely publicized by the state since 1963 as a human embodiment of the ideal youth under Mao. He was selfless, loyal to Mao, modest, and dedicated. His aspiration, written in his diary, was to be “nothing more than a small but essential screw in the collective engine of the revolution.”²³ “Learning from Lei Feng” campaigns both before and during the Cultural Revolution produced a political mythology that preached practising basic good deeds and absolute devotion to Mao.²⁴ In localities, “living Lei Fengs” and “active elements of learning from Lei Feng” were selected to award those who were idealistic socialists, and some outstanding ones were publicized as local models through their speeches, publications, movies, and operas. Following Lei Feng, Ouyang Hai (1940-1963) and Wang Jie (1942-1965) were popular military models and subjects of many political education campaigns. They and many more local variations shared in a common loyalty to the Party and willingness to risk their lives for the public good but not for personal gains.

²⁰ Louise Edwards, “Military celebrity in China: the evolution of “heroic and model servicemen,” in Louise Edwards and Elaine Jeffreys ed., *Celebrity in China*, (Pokfulam: Hong Kong University Press, 2010): 21- 43.

²¹ Gay Garland Reed, *The Lei Feng phenomenon in the PRC*, (Virginia: University of Virginia, 1991), 16.

²² Reed, *The Lei Feng phenomenon in the PRC*, 16.

²³ Mary Sheridan, ‘The Emulation of Heroes,’ *The China Quarterly* 33 (1968): 15.

²⁴ Elaine Jeffreys, “Modern China’s Idols: Heroes, Role Models, Stars and Celebrities,” *Journal of Multidisciplinary International Studies* 9.1 (January 2012): 11.

It is evident in the letters that Wang Shu envisioned himself as a “living Lei Feng.” Wang explicitly swore to be “a screw that never rusts.” Wang understood the Lei Feng spirit comprehensively – it was not only about altruism and hard-working, but also obedience and anonymity. According to Lei Feng, “it is only by the many, many interconnected and fixed screws that the machine can move freely, increasing its enormous work power. Though a screw is small, its use is beyond estimation.”²⁵ Aspiring to be the screw in the machine for the Maoist revolution, Wang understood his “sent-down” life as an essential part of the formidable nation-building project.²⁶ Wang thought of the movement, not from his personal perspective and his gains and losses, but the nation’s and the Party’s perspectives. He was attempting to be selfless, and only thought about the “public matter” but not the “personal matter.” While many of his fellow educated youth found their repetitive labour meaningless and unbearably boring sooner or later, Wang had been fuelled with enthusiasm for physical labour and political activities for years. He took pride in his hard work, which was rewarded by his slow but steady promotions. For most of the time, Wang had no trouble abiding orders and went wherever his superiors sent him and did the tasks assigned to him. He did not question the effectiveness or the genuine impact of the tasks. Wang staged himself as a dedicated teenager, instead of a victim of coercive dislocation and harsh labour, contrasting with many memoirs, which painted miserable and wasted years. His letters allow us to imagine: How and why did adolescents like Wang Shu try to live like the national hero, Lei Feng?

²⁵ Lei Feng, *Lei Feng Riji Shiwenxuan* [Lei Feng’s selected daires and poems] (Beijing: Zhanshi Publishing House, 1982), 77.

²⁶ Wang, Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu.

The “sent-down” years

“Ever-lasting loyalty to Chairman Mao!” is how the first letter in the collection starts, on 25th October, 1968. Settling in Harbin Youth Farm did not seem to trouble or shock Wang. It is partly because a military farm had the best material conditions, compared to working in a village production team.²⁷ Wang got a cotton uniform and a military flurry hat, preparing for the freezing cold in the winter. He was soon occupied with the labour in the horse unit till 1969.

Time slipped by on the farm. The third letter was written on January 2, 1970, when he had just gotten back from visiting his family. By then Wang was hustling in the cooking unit, preparing for the new year celebrations. In the festive time, he learned how to make steam buns and enjoyed the special new year feast with beef dumplings. The son playfully signed his letter with a cute little icon of a tree.

When he was not cooking, Wang and his unit volunteered to dig tunnels for military usage. During the Cultural Revolution, China had split with the Soviet Union and a war between the two communist countries became more and more plausible. To defend against the communist giant equipped with nuclear weapons and missiles, the Chinese state mobilized the people to dig underground tunnels and burrows.²⁸ When students and workers alike finished their day-time duties, they spent night after night digging holes, removing dirt, and stacking bricks. In the border area, the anxiety for Sino-Soviet conflicts resulted in an ante-bellum state. Unfortunately, Wang’s enthusiasm was met with great difficulties posed by the breezing weather and frozen soil in the coldest part of China. Worse still, the cadres of his company were

²⁷ Yang, *The Red Guard Generation and Political Activism in China*, 104.

²⁸ Michael S. Gerson, *The Sino-Soviet Border Conflict Deterrence, Escalation, and the Threat of Nuclear War in 1969*, (USA: Centre for Naval Analyses, November 2010): 40-41.

not supportive towards their attempt. Yet, Wang and his comrades were prepared to move them with their relentless, overnight digging. “We are not afraid of the sky and the soil! Every dig we made is a bullet shooting at the Soviet revisionists!” The immense eagerness for fighting against the revisionists was still flowing in the blood of educated youth, at least in this company.

In the freezing March, Wang’s duty shifted to pasturing horses overnight, as he was sent back to the horse unit. In addition, his company was responsible for artistic performances in regiment meetings. Wang modestly mocked his own lack of artistic talent and experience, and thus he was content to act as a minor character.

The opera they performed was not the eight model operas, as ubiquitous as they were in the Cultural Revolution, but an opera that was written by their regiment. “Ode of Jin Xuehe” was a short opera celebrating Jin Xuehe, a male educated youth from Harbin also exiled to Wang’s regiment. On a rainy morning in May of 1969, some big wood trunks slipped from a car trunk accidentally.²⁹ In this critical moment, Jin used his body to block the trunks from falling onto the other six educated youths in front of the car. The heavy trunks hit his chest, and blood spilt from Jin’s mouth – he died immediately. Like other Chinese who self-sacrificed their life for their comrades, Jing was heroized, reported on local news and was promoted as a model soldier in the regiment. Jin was only one among many of the state-endorsed local variations of Lei Feng, who shared a similar ordinary background, did good deeds in their everyday lives, and

²⁹ Jia Hongtu, “Zhiqing gushi: Jin Xuehe sheji jui ren dao zai chun yu li” 知青故事：金學和捨己救人倒在春雨里 [The story of the educated youth: Jin Xuehe sacrificed himself to save others and died in the rain in the spring], (4 March, 2019) Accessed through <https://kknews.cc/zh-hk/story/mplpegg.html> (Please see Chicago Style manual on how you should cite digital works).

Jia Hongtu, *Qingchuan 1968* 青春1968 [Youth 1968], (Beijing: Zuo jia Chubanshe 2015), 22-27.

died heroically for the people and the Party. They were shaped by the state propaganda machines to be idols and role models for everyone in the country.³⁰

As an adolescent who grew up under the state-dominated socialization and education, it is no surprise that Wang internalized the official glorification of Jin's death. Wang did not grieve for Jin's death, nor felt angry about the man-made tragedy. Instead, he felt educated and inspired by the deceased. When he performed in the opera and praised Jin, Wang learned from and immortalized him. "Every time we act," Wang wrote, "it's like Jin Xuehe standing next to me like it used to, tapping my shoulder and leading me to progress!"³¹ In his words, the tragedy of Jin was an act of heroism, which he greatly admired.

The death of Jin perhaps fueled Wang's aspiration to be a "living Lei Feng". Ordinary youth in normal circumstances could not imagine emulating any god-like heroes. But when they were put in military production farms, got their soldier uniforms, and dug tunnels to defend against the Soviets, they were one step closer to becoming a military model. Additionally, the ones who had been chosen to be public heroes were once ordinary people, just like them, and what they did were achievable by these ordinary youth in the rural area as long as they were altruistic and not afraid to sacrifice themselves. The publicity machinery evaluated those "just-like-you-and-me" individuals into national models, and there was no reason for Wang Shu not wanting to become a local celebrity when he definitely had the chance to become one and saw his comrade – Jin Xuehe – already made to be one.

³⁰ Mary Sheridan, 'The Emulation of Heroes,' 47.

³¹ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. March, 1970.

Looking up to all the heroic models, Wang also actively participated in all kinds of political activities and campaigns. He read and reread Mao's "The Three Classical Pieces" (*Laosanpian*) – and this was just one of his many rituals of worshipping Mao. He enthusiastically accepted the Party's indoctrination on having the correct "class stance" and stood firm to his class position. In May 1970, there was an education program against indecency in Wang's regiment, in which educated youth were evaluated by the local authorities. The program did not affect Wang personally, whose father was just pronounced as a "five-good cadre" (*wuhao ganbu*). But he was glad that the ones with "class issues" were banned from the construction project for national defence.

In the torrid heat of July of the same year, Wang for the first time complained about the food in the camp. As the rations of wheat were not sent to the regiment this year, all he could have were mix-grain steamed buns (*mantou*), which were so hard to swallow. However, Wang's complaint did not last for a few lines – he was quick in comforting himself and his parents passionately that the bitterness he was experiencing was nothing compared to that of the Red Army. "The Red Army climbed through snowy mountains and lived arduously, isn't our experience incomparable? We will do anything, and will put more effort in completing even harder tasks for the sake of revolution!"³²

Wang was as self-reassuring as before even when his tasks got tougher. In mid-summer, his assignment changed from feeding horses overnight to mowing in the field along with thirty youths in his company. Unfortunately, it did not start well – on the first day, as they were setting up the tents, there was a rainstorm. The rain lingered for days, hindering their labour progress.

³² Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. July, 1970.

Surprisingly, Wang thought that it was the most fruitful time by far in his life, and described the days of heavy labour as delightful. While his work was mostly monotonous, he never once complained about it. It is not because the labour wasn't high intensity enough, but it is because Wang believed that the nation needs his tasks for economic development and military defence, as the "revolutionary machine" cannot run without every "screw." His satisfaction and sense of validity were based on his perception of the contributions he made to the revolutionary progress of the nation. Thus, the tougher the working process was, the more self-fulfilling he was, regardless of the actual result of his tasks.

Wang's physical burden was heavier when there was a major transferal of educated youth in the camp. More than 400 people were transferred to another farm in the region due to an insufficient food supply. There were too many people, too few lands, and the transportation was inconvenient. There were only eight hundred people left in the camp with no newcomer in the year. Although his work became more intense than ever, Wang kept his optimistic tone and faith in the Party – "the future of the camp is promising!"³³

After the season of mowing, Wang devoted himself to the equally tiresome task of harvesting wheat. The workload was so heavy that no one was allowed to take leave to visit home. While time was tight for harvesting, Wang, unfortunately, got acute stomach flu. But Wang assured his parents, "My body is still very healthy! I recovered!" The youth always convinced himself that he is healthy, and disregarded any physical discomfort. This is a product of the state evocation: Mao's words and thoughts can transcend and overcome all weaknesses of physical bodies. Selfless socialist heroic characters whom Wang tried to live up to take no notice of the

³³ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. August 5, 1970.

feeling of pain. But perhaps more so than his words, Wang's torn tank top, pants and shoes were more accurate reflections of the harshness of labour.

Amid the strenuous production activities in August, Wang wrote an unusual letter to home. He mentioned his thoughts on romantic relationships for the first time. He led into the topic very indirectly:

Recently, I am thinking about how to contribute my life to the revolution, and I should not start thinking about personal matters too early. No matter how significant personal matters are, they are unimportant; no matter how minor the national and revolutionary matters are, they are important. There are some things that I have never told you about. There was a time when I was determined to never consider personal matters. But recently I got some new thoughts, though I am holding the same basic principles. Some topics are hard to talk about... Mom, please don't worry, I will not make mistake in this aspect."³⁴

The timid son circled around the topic, feeling anxious to disclose any details to his parents. This euphemism is even more evident when Wang spoke of a "minor incident" to his parents – some of his fellows joked about him and a girl. The female educated youth was working in the medical unit after she and Wang had worked together in the propaganda unit for a while. Wang nervously clarified that those rumours were untrue, and he did not think about the matter at all. "I did not take it seriously. I thought I was too young, and should not think about this. Please believe me!"³⁵ He was really trying to convince his parents, and perhaps himself, that he would not start a romantic relationship. But then, why would he mention the affair at all if he was not hinting something to them? At the age of 21, with no previous experience in romance, and no one to talk to around him who would not gossip about it, he seems to be testing out their attitude and subtly seeking their advice. His indirectness was understandable, not only due to his timid

³⁴ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. August, 1970.

³⁵ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. August, 1970.

personality, but also the intrinsic risk of any romantic liaisons. Wang felt inappropriate to put any thoughts on romance – as his generation was educated to love the ‘public’ (*gong*, proletarian) and oppose the ‘private’ (*shi*, personal or capitalism) matters, and being selfish could be a crime. Wang was politically correct that romance was a “personal matter,” which one should prioritize after the “public good.”³⁶ On top of that, having any intimate relations with the opposite sex was considered indecent and a moral stain.³⁷ In his published diary, for example, Lei Feng likewise denied any romantic relations with females.³⁸ Wang tried to show his parents that he was not intimidated by the gossip, as “there is nothing of such sort (of romance), what should I be afraid of?”³⁹ His rhetorical question later got a genuine answer.

Oddly, in September of the same year, the usually energetic Wang was feeling miserable: “Today I am feeling terrible.”⁴⁰ He started his letter after the habitual heading of “Ever-lasting loyalty to the great leader Chairman Mao.” The day before, he fell on a harrow and had a very deep cut on his right hand. He rushed to the hospital and got three stitches. The next day, the doctor told the injured that his wound was infected and gave him an injection. The pain-stricken Wang used his right hand to write slowly and awkwardly, inking the papers with almost illegible Chinese characters. What upset him, even more, was the departure of his close friend, Feng Qingguang, from the farm. Feng’s parents were old cadres and recently retired, so Feng accompanied them to go back to their hometown. The Hubei-originated youth left in a hurry, leaving no time to say goodbye to Wang, who was still out in the grass field. Wang felt disconsolate: “There were fewer and fewer people on the farm, my comrades left one by one, I

³⁶ Yang, 107.

³⁷ Emily Honig, "Socialist sex: The cultural revolution revisited," *Modern China* 29.2 (2003): 143-175.

³⁸ Tian Xiaofei. "The Making of a Hero.: Lei Feng and Some Issues of Historiography." *The People's Republic of China at 60*, (Brill, 2011), 304.

Bonnin and Horko, *The Lost Generation*, 325.

³⁹ Wang Shu. *Xiaoshu jiashu*. August, 1970.

⁴⁰ Wang Shu. *Xiaoshu jiashu*. September 7, 1970.

am feeling very sad. Where will I be in the future? I have to think about these questions...”⁴¹

The gradual departing of Wang’s fellows reflected a wider phenomenon – many educated youths were attempting to return to their cities or get relocated. In fact, as soon as weeks and months after the urban youth were sent down, their parents tried to get them out of the impoverished countryside.⁴² The usual tactics were to claim illnesses or family issues, though both require certain proof and approval from local cadres, which were not easy to obtain in 1970.⁴³ Many colleagues of Wang were so desperate to return to their home city that they employed their personal connections, bribed the people in power, or even sickened themselves. Feng Qingguang, for instance, might well be mobilizing his parents’ (as cadres) social network to leave the farm, as parents’ relocation was usually not a sufficient reason. Even when the majority of the educated youth did not get the chance to return to their cities, there were still constant parting and social disconnections caused by frequent collective relocations. He told his parents in the letter, “Today another platoon was sent away. Watching our comrades leaving, many female comrades cried out loud, and some male comrades also teared up. I did not tear up at all. Since the year of (19)68... all four people in my class left, so did the twelfth in my school... I really want to cry out loud under my blanket in the house. But how is crying useful? I better think about the future!”⁴⁴ Despite trying to be tough, his words revealed his mixed feelings – his insecurity, vulnerability, and numbness.

⁴¹ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. September 7, 1970.

⁴² Yang, *The Red Guard Generation and Political Activism in China*, 115.

⁴³ Thomas B Gold, "Back to the city: The return of Shanghai's educated youth," *China Quarterly* (1980): 755-770.

⁴⁴ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. September 11, 1970.

Three days later, the usual, cheerful Wang was back, and he wrote to his family about the omnipresent topic – work. A dozen days after his hand got stitches, Wang was assigned to watch over the wheatfields overnight. The nights in the north were shivering cold, but Wang powered through whenever he thought of “Chairman Mao’s teaching.” As always, Wang deeply believed that “Mao Zedong Thoughts” could help him conquer all difficulties, including physical fatigue, sleep deprivation, and all the issues in work.⁴⁵ As his hand recovered, his platoon participated in the concrete mixing and casting construction project for national defence. Wang casually mentioned that he “fainted once because of the smell of gasoline.” Again, the son tried to make his discomfort sound like nothing. Instead of complaining about the incident, Wang felt sorry for leaving the production battlefield in the key moment. In return for his hard work, on the eve of the National Day (October 1st), he was awarded the Commendation of the Battalion, to which he dedicated his family as a present. Was Wang an exception for always performing affectionate gestures to his beloved parents in the Red Guard generation, which has been characterized for their rebellion against and hostility towards their parents’ generation?⁴⁶

Wang believed that he could visit home in the near future. A new Circular announced that educated youth working for two years or more could request a leave. Along with other fifty sent-down youth of 1968, Wang was eligible for the opportunity. He wrote with deep sincerity, “Dad and Mom please don’t worry, we will see each other soon.”⁴⁷ Unfortunately, he was let down. In his next letter, Wang disappointingly told his parents that he could not visit home that year. The political commissar stated that sent-down youth could only visit home once every three years, and the poor son had to wait for at least half a year. Wang missed his family so

⁴⁵ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. September 14, 1970.

⁴⁶ For example, Martin Singer marked “resentment to older generation” as a defining characteristic of the educated youth. See Martin Singer, *Educated youth and the cultural revolution in China*, (Michigan: University of Michigan Press, 1971), 80-81.

⁴⁷ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. October 19, 1970.

much that he dreamt of seeing them many times, and the feeling was even stronger when his sister and brother both went back home. Wang begged, "Please send me a photo of the whole family, and I will stick my photo on it, so it looks like we are being together."⁴⁸ He did not envision that there would be a time when the whole family reunite again. His solicitude for his family was so sincere and heartfelt, that his self-reassurance of the need to contribute to the Party and the nation seems pale. Wang no longer voiced his disappointment a month later. The debates on political lines in his platoon took away all his energy. He engaged with the debates personally:

All comrades were not willing to speak. I did not dare to speak up too at first. But that was not the behaviour of a true revolutionary, one cannot just by-stand the erroneous line prevailed in the platoon. Some leaders in the platoon supported the erroneous line, and their fellows helped spread it. Therefore in the meeting, we who were the minority made up the courage to speak up. Perhaps we will be the targets of revenge of some leaders, but being revolutionary means being fearless of attacks and vengeance.⁴⁹

Seeing himself as Mao's revolutionary successor, the young man considered speaking against the bureaucrats as risky but necessary. Indeed, he was situated in the turmoil of the Cultural Revolution, when the state structure was dissolving, and one's political fate was more dependent on personal relations than ever.⁵⁰ Young students and power-holding cadres were both vulnerable to political accusations and drastic changes in status. Wang's speech posted risk to either himself or the leaders of the platoon. But were these young people being subversive? Probably not, as it is evident here: "Please don't worry, Dad. I am very calm... We

⁴⁸ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. October 19, 1970.

⁴⁹ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. October, 1970.

⁵⁰ Thomas B Gold, "After comradeship: personal relations in China since the Cultural Revolution," *China Quarterly* (1985): 657-670.

must give our comments to the leaders, but our motive is to help them. One day, cadres who made mistakes will understand.”⁵¹

Unflappably, Wang also told his parent’s bad news – his blanket and coat were all burnt down in a big fire. He simply notified his parents and apologized in advance for using up more money to buy replacements, on which he later spent his monthly salary. It was surprising, even by the standard of his time, that he did not complain nor panic when he looked at the ashes of all his important belongings, but purely stated that it was a “misfortune.” This shows how Wang cared little about his personal, *private* possessions. In his subsequent letters, he repeatedly reaffirmed his parents, who had every reason to, not to worry and pleaded with them not to send him any additional things.⁵²

The undisturbed Wang told his family cordially that a “comrade” was going to visit home. On the eve of the Chinese New Year of 1971, Yip Cuihua was sent by Wang to visit his family on the way back to her home. Interestingly, this female educated youth was the one with whom he previously denied having a close relationship with. He wrote: “Let her tell you my situation. We knew each other well. But don’t let her bring anything for me.”⁵³ And that was his remarks on Yip – nothing explicit about their relationship, but enough disclosure for his parents to get a hunch. In Mao’s China, Confucius’s ideal of minimal heterosociality still triumphed over the Marxist ideal of eliminating gender differences.⁵⁴ Under this social norm, Wang’s parents would have sensed something when Wang mentioned a “she.”

⁵¹ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. October, 1970.

⁵² Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. October, 1970.

⁵³ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. January 14, 1971.

⁵⁴ Zhang Dening and Yue Jianyi, *Zhongguo zhiqing qinglian baogao: qingchun jidi* 中國知青情戀報告：青春極地 [Report on love and sex among China’s sent-down youth: the pinnacle of youth], vol 2 (Beijing: Guangming ribao chubanshe, 1998): 2.

The timid son finally spoke more straightforwardly – though still far from direct – on the matter in his next letter.

But there is a matter laid upon me, it's hard to deal with and I'm inexperienced with it. At first, I didn't want to tell you about it, but in order not to make any mistakes, I have to tell you about this. It's my personal matter. Specifically, it's about her and me. We cared deeply about each other... In the beginning, none of us had put too much thought into it, but then gradually our relationship deepened. We were now in the stage where none expressed our feelings, but we both understood it in our hearts.⁵⁵

Wang described his romantic relationship shyly, and in brief, words pictured out a Platonic romance with a down-to-earth, upright girl. At the same time, Wang was confused about the relationship. And as always, he asked for his parents' advice when he was uncertain. "I did not know why I told you about this," Wang confessed, "but I thought I should not hide anything from my parents, and it helps to let you two learn about it."

Later, Wang regretted telling his parents about Yip. It was not out of shame or concealment, but he felt guilty for making his parents worried:

I should not have told you about this matter in the previous letter, as you had been thinking about it repeatedly overnight and it was holding you up... Now how should I put it? Maybe I am a bit embarrassed, but let me speak of it briefly... Now I am in the fifth company, and she is in the medical unit. I told her to learn the essay "Memory of Norman Bethune" (*Jinian Baiquien*) and write notes persistently. Although we do not meet very often now, we have the opportunity to see each other in battalion meetings.⁵⁶

While Wang's words portrayed a rather distant and aromantic relationship, he planned to marry the girl and form their own family at the age of thirty. In a page of grid paper, Wang illustrated

⁵⁵ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. January 14, 1971.

⁵⁶ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. February, 1971.

a smooth flow of his romance with Yip, based on their comradeship, commitment, and shared political stance. Compared to his zeal for revolutionary labour and study, he was rather detached when describing his relationship. If there was passion and limerence in this romance, he hid it very well in the letters.

Meanwhile, Wang's life at work seems to be on track. He was still getting his hands on the hydraulic construction. The hardworking young man was climbing up the vocational ladder steadily – in February 1971, he was promoted to the deputy platoon leader, then later platoon leader, with an increase in wages.

After many repetitive days in April, Wang's work took a turn. He was sent to a construction site in the army in Bulisu, a town in Northern China. The transferral brought a major change in Wang's romantic life – he had stopped seeing Yip. He told his parents:

I've told her I will never find her again. In one way or another, it was to leave her quickly to avoid more pain in the future. So I was determined to come here to the new battalion for the construction project. And I was really sure, as the fifth battalion was overstaffed with 1500 people, I will definitely not be able to go back. We did not meet when I left. I wrote a letter to her on the last day as a comrade... I saw her outside the regiment the day I left, she smiled at me from afar, but I looked aside and stepped into the car.⁵⁷

Thus the young couple saw each other for the one last time in silence, and never going to meet again. Unlike the parting with his battalion in the train station, in which he admitted bluntly he broke down in tears, Wang did not show his sadness, though the breakup was a heavy blow on his perception of romance. "As for my personal matter, to be honest, before 25 years old I will not think about it again. I am prepared to devote all my energy to the revolutionary work."⁵⁸

⁵⁷ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. April, 1971.

⁵⁸ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. April, 1971.

He seemed to be living up to his vow in that period and did not mention the topic in the subsequent letters. In the new site, he and other all-male “monks companies” were prepared to toil around the clock for the construction with explosives and machines. Wang earned an improved diet as the working condition was harsher and sleeping time shortened. He got a ration of rice, white flour, and meat, which was considered very decent for the youth in the decade – most sent-down youth-only dreamt of getting away from starvation.⁵⁹ He did need the nutrition to support his hard labour. The ceaseless body could not stand up straight every day after work. Though with a tired physique, Wang still asked his parents to send him more books on politics, especially on heroic models, and engineering, so he could read in his free time. In this new place, the son did not have a lot of friends, thus he pleaded, “Dad and mom, please also send me more letters. Sister and little brother too, send some please.”⁶⁰

It soon came to his birthday on November 2, 1971. “I was lucky this year. The cooking unit sent us noodles with eggs. All comrades said I was blessed to have noodles on my birthday. At night, they accompanied me to the train station to buy candies. It’s a happy day.”⁶¹ Happiness was that simple to Wang at the age of 22.

Wang shifted his focus of “personal matter” from romance to his own prospects. Wang reminded himself not to equate a “promising future” with education qualifications. In the mind of the 22-year-old, introspection and self-reflection were processes of internalizing state propaganda and mobilizations. He often reminded himself to put the interest of the Party first, to base himself on the needs of the revolution. But for the first time, perhaps triggered by the

⁵⁹ Dikötter, *The Cultural Revolution*, 196.

⁶⁰ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. July 21, 1971.

⁶¹ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. November 2, 1971.

letters sent from his friends who got into universities, Wang wrote about the possibility of going into the university in 1972. He listed out the preconditions of applying to a university in Harbin. “I seemed very far from the conditions, but I will fight for it!”⁶² Indeed, Wang was right about how hard it was to get recruited by universities, at the time when rumours about admissions and returning to the cities were flying around in the nation, and many educated youths could not wait to flock back to their urban homes. As resistance against rustication grew, cohorts of educated youth were allowed to return to their cities based on medical or family conditions in 1972.⁶³ Wang’s desire to go to a university did not make him slack off at work –Wang hustled around his labour, “I did not stop for even a minute in the battalion. I did not even have time to read the letters.” His half-a-page short letter was proof that he indeed was very busy.⁶⁴

Wang’s life is a mystery to us for the next two years, as there was no letter of the period in the collection. One thing we know is that he did not settle in his home city. Instead, in July 1974, he was a teacher of the ninth grade in the battalion. “It is a tiresome job to take care of the class, but I have a close relationship with my students, and most of them behaved and are considerate.”⁶⁵ Wang was a caring teacher – he spent his salary on his students and visited their families often. Being an always loving brother to his siblings, Wang bought a pair of boots for his younger sister and sent money to his younger brother.

Meanwhile, he began a heterosexual relationship for the first time since his romantic relationship with Yip died out. A male comrade in his regiment introduced Wang to his younger sister, another female educated youth. “She is three years younger than me, shorter than me,

⁶² Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. April, 1972.

⁶³ Gold, "Back to the city." Bonnin and Horko, 88-93.

⁶⁴ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. April, 1972.

⁶⁵ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. July 3, 1974.

has a healthy body, her family lives in the Harbin mechanic factory, her father is a party member and a cadre, a photo is attached in this letter. We have been exchanging letters a few times, she has mailed me items like pants. I think that is the deal.”⁶⁶ Without mentioning the name of the girl, Wang introduced his partner to his parents in plain, even objective, wordings. However, in his next and also the last letter of the collection, dated February 25, 1975, Wang announced the death of the relationship:

I wrote a letter to Peng (the female educated youth), I was saying that since we were not a match in many aspects, let’s call it off. But she wrote to me, saying that she would not find another person aside from me, which made me feel embarrassed. But I was being outright, putting the reasonings out. Our relationship will not last, so calling this off will not have any long-term effects and extra responsibilities. I am devoted to working.⁶⁷

That was how Wang’s second attempt with a woman ended, so did his collection of letters. Every word in the letters shows how Wang Shu tried his best to emulate the heroic models in the years he spent in the most northeastern rural part of China. He largely lived out the Lei Feng spirit – love for the Party, for Mao, for labour, and for the people. Among the many faces of Lei Feng, he resembled the national idol the most in his aspiration to be a rustless screw in the collective – eagerly following superiors’ commands and overachieving at the most ordinary or tedious positions. The sent-down movement provided a platform for Wang to actualize the ideals and channel his ceaseless energy into manual labour that socialist societies celebrate. He was obedient to the orders from the local government of frequently transferring to various farms and units, even though it meant tougher and unfamiliar tasks and parting from acquaintances – he believed that the Party would send him to wherever most needed. Being given arduous military and agricultural tasks in the border area, Wang could see himself to be another “living

⁶⁶ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. April, 1974.

⁶⁷ Wang Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. February 25, 1975.

Lei Feng” and sacrifice his life like Jin Xuehe. Although clothed with a modest tone, Wang Shu was actually proud of himself, of his hard work, and dedication to the country – the “sent-down years” was largely a rewarding journey to him.

However, unlike Lei Feng who was martyred and perfected through state-regulated propagation, Wang did not absolutely adhere to the state ideals. The rebellious spirit targeting authorities – against local leaders and one’s parents – was not found in Wang. He was a son filled with Confucius filial piety – constantly easing the worries of his parents, caring for his siblings, sending his salary back home, seeking consent from parents in romantic relationships, being humble before his parents... For his family, Wang tried to buy food from the “private markets.” As scholars pointed out, traditional Chinese ethics persisted through family education even under the anti-Confucianism culture during the Cultural Revolution, in which sons and daughters were still taught to obey.⁶⁸ Moreover, Wang’s letters display his shortcomings in acting and writing, emotions and moments of vulnerability, as well as failure in romantic attempts.

⁶⁸ Chen, "Lost in revolution and reform," 222.

Conclusion

The young Wang Shu was uncritically satisfied with devoting his youth to labouring and political activities. He found meaning in these meticulous tasks and exhausting days by internalizing and identifying with Mao's promulgation. For most of the time, the young man was passionate, motivated and delighted. He represents one of the successful cases of Chinese state inculcation – for Pan Yihong concludes quite precisely, “this was a complex generation. In its members, idealism, heroism, and self-sacrifice were combined with a lack of independent thinking.”⁶⁹

At the same time, the details sketched in his letters add a personal touch to the young ideological-driven man, who was boring, but real. These minor flaws and personal characteristics show that he was just one of the millions of ordinary nameless dislocated youth in China inspired by the Lei Feng spirit. And for that, his story was probably too boring for many editors, publishers, and readers. Dominating educated-youth literature, which focuses on life-changing, dramatic sufferings or achievements, seems to give too little space for us to imagine boring, non-captivating sent-down experiences. Daily routines and trivial matters, perhaps most susceptible to memory loss, in fact, made up the largest part of the educated youth's realities. Wang's letters humanized the educated youth. It bridges the gap between the two opposite popular images of educated youth – helpless victims or indoctrinated fanatics. He was constantly seeking self-improvement, but also single-minded; he adhered to Chinese traditional, but was also a believer of Mao; he toiled around the clock, but also calculated his salary; he was passionate about revolutionary projects, but also missed his family deeply; he celebrated heroic deaths, but also looked for opportunities to go into a university. Wang's letters

⁶⁹ Pan, *Tempered in the revolutionary furnace*, 216.

are gateways for readers to reimagine the fabric of daily life in the sent-down movement. His narrative was so down-to-earth with details in daily life, that one perhaps finds him not as distant to us as we thought. He is an authentic example of the successful state imposition of the Lei Feng model. He reminds us that another vast dislocation project with tragic consequences is not impossible and unacceptable under the regime of the CCP with ordinary teenagers like Wang who can engage in state mobilizations without a thought on its shortcomings and dangers. It is important for historians to look into the Down to the Countryside Movement carefully and closely without the benefits of hindsight, and understand the sent-down generation as they were, so as to reflect on the nature, impact, and replicability of the massive rustication project.

Bibliography

Letters

Lu, Rong. Letters to his parents, 1970-79. In *Yige Shanghai zhiqing de 223 feng jiashu* 一個上海知青的223封家書. [223 family letters from a Shanghai educated youth] Shanghai: Shanghai shehui kexueyuan chubanshe, 2009.

Yang, Dezhong, and Li Guanzhen. Letters to children, 1953-76. In Yang Haiyan, and Feng Xiaohong ed. *Wenge jiashu: xiegei haizimen de xin* 文革家書: 寫給孩子們的信 [Letters from Home: Cultural Revolution] Hong Kong: Old Wall Group Hong Kong Company Limited, 2017.

Wang, Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu [Little Shu's family letters], 1968-74. Acquired on January, 2020 through Kongfuzi jiushuwang, <https://www.kongfz.com/>

Books

Bernstein, Thomas P. *Up to the Mountains and Down to the Villages: The Transfer of Youth from Urban to Rural China*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 1977.

Bonnin, Michel and Horko Krystyna. *The lost generation: The rustication of China's educated youth (1968–1980)*. Shatin: The Chinese University of Hong Kong Press, 2013.

Dikötter, Frank. *The Cultural Revolution: A People's History, 1962–1976*. Bloomsbury Publishing USA, 2016.

Edwards, Louise and Elaine Jeffreys ed. *Celebrity in China*. Pokfulam: Hong Kong University Press, 2010.

Gerson, Michael S. *The Sino-Soviet Border Conflict Deterrence, Escalation, and the Threat of Nuclear War in 1969*. USA: Centre for Naval Analyses, November 2010.

Gu, H. ed. *Zhongguo Zhishi Qingnian Shangshan Xiaxiang Chimo* 中國知識青年上山下鄉始末 [The whole story of Zhiqing UMDC in China]. Beijing: China Procuratorial Press, 1997.

Lao, Bian. *Qingchuan 1968* 青春1968 [Youth 1968]. Beijing: Zuoja Chubanshe, 2015.

Jiang, Yarong and David Ashley. *Mao's children in the new China: voices from the Red Guard generation*. London: Psychology Press, 2000.

Larso, Wendy. *From Ah Q to Lei Feng: Freud and Revolutionary Spirit in 20th Century China*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2009.

Lei, Feng. *Lei Feng Riji Shiwenxuan* [Lei Feng's selected dairies and poems] Beijing: Zhanshi Publishing House, 1982.

Liu, Xiaomen. *Zhongguo zhiqingshi: Dachao* 中國知青史：大潮 (1953–1968) [History of Zhiqing in China: The spring tide (1966–1980)] Beijing: China Social Sciences Press, 1998.

Ou, Nianzhong and Liang Yongkang ed.. Laura Maynard trans. *Mao's Lost Children: Stories of the Rusticated Youth of China's Cultural Revolution*. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2015.

Pan, Yihong. *Tempered in the Revolutionary Furnace: China's Youth in the Rustication Movement*. Lanham, Md.: Lexington, 2002.

Reed, Gay Garland. *The Lei Feng phenomenon in the PRC*. Virginia: University of Virginia, 1991.

Schram, Stuart R. ed. *Authority, Participation and Cultural Change in China: Essays by a European Study Group*. Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 1973.

Shapiro, Judith. *Mao's war against nature: Politics and the environment in revolutionary China*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001.

Singer, Martin. *Educated youth and the cultural revolution in China*. Michigan: University of Michigan Press, 1971.

Xu, Zidong. *Weile wangque de jiti jiyi: jiedu 50 pian wenge xiaoshuo* 為了忘卻的集體記憶：解讀五十篇文革小說 [For the forgotten collective memory: an analysis of 50 samples of Cultural Revolution fiction]. Beijing: Sanlian shudian, 2000.

Yang, Guobin. *The Red Guard Generation and Political Activism in China*. New York: Columbia University Press, 2016.

You, Yang. *Educated youth should go to the rural areas: A tale of education, employment and social values*. Working Paper, 2018.

Zhang, Dening and Yue Jianyi. *Zhongguo zhiqing qinglian baogao: qingchun jidi* 中國知青情戀報告：青春極地 [Report on love and sex among China's sent-down youth: the pinnacle of youth]. Vol 2. Beijing: Guangming ribao chubanshe, 1998.

Journal articles

Bonnin, Michel "Restricted, distorted but alive: The memory of the "lost generation" of Chinese educated youth," *The China Quarterly* 227 (2016).

Chen, Yi, Fan Ziyang, Gu Xiaomin, and Zhou LiAn. "Arrival of Young Talent: The Send-Down Movement and Rural Education in China." *American Economic Review* 110.11 (2020): 3393-430.

Chen, Yixin. "Lost in revolution and reform: The socioeconomic pains of China's red guards' generation, 1966–1996." *Journal of Contemporary China* 8.21 (1999): 219-39.

Chiu, Stephen WK and Eva P. W. Hung. "The Lost Generation Life Course Dynamics and Xiangang in China," *Modern China* 29.2, (April 2003): 204-36.

Gold, Thomas B. "After comradeship: Personal relations in China since the Cultural Revolution." *China Quarterly* (1985): 657-75.

He, Guanghan. "Xiexiang ganbu jiashu(1977)" 下鄉幹部家書(1977) [Family letters from a sent-down cadre (1977)]. *Tianya* 3 (2002): 80-92.

Honig, Emily. "Socialist sex: The cultural revolution revisited." *Modern China* 29, 2 (2003): 143-75.

Jeffreys, Elaine. "Modern China's Idols: Heroes, Role Models, Stars and Celebrities," *Journal of Multidisciplinary International Studies* 9, 1 (January 2012): 1-32.

Sheridan, Mary. 'The Emulation of Heroes,' *The China Quarterly* 33 (1968): 47-72.

Tian, Xiaofei. "The Making of a Hero: Lei Feng and Some Issues of Historiography." *The People's Republic of China at 60* (2011): 291-305.

White, Gordon D. "The politics of hsia-hsiang youth." *China Quarterly* (1974): 491-517.

Yang, Guobin. "China's zhiqing generation: nostalgia, identity, and cultural resistance in the 1990s." *Modern China* 29, 3 (2003): 267-96.

Zarrow, Peter. "Meanings of China's Cultural Revolution: Memoirs of exile." *Positions* 7, 1 (1999): 165-91.

"Back to the city: The return of Shanghai's educated youth." *China Quarterly* (1980): 755-70.

"The 'Lost Generation': Its Definition and Its Role in Today's Chinese Elite Politics." *China in Transition* 73, 1 (Spring 2006): 245-74.

Website content

Chen, Guonan. “418 feng jiashu de ganqing gushi” 418封家書的情感故事 [The stories of 418 family letters] (3 July 2007) Accessed through

<http://jiashu.ruc.edu.cn/jsbl/zqjs/33ec935c0f684912b87e0723538b9162.htm>.

Huang, Shengfan, “Daxing Enling famu renji” 大興安嶺伐木日記 [Diary of lumbering in Daxing anling] Accessed through <http://news.ifeng.com/history/special/zhiqing/huangshengfan/>.

Jia, Hongtu. “Zhiqing gushi: Jin Xuehe sheji juren daozei chunyu” 知青故事：金學和捨己救人倒在春雨里 [The story of the educated youth: Jin Xuehe sacrificed himself to save others and died in the rain in the spring]. 4 March 2019. Accessed through <https://kknews.cc/zh-hk/story/implpegg.html>.

Laobian. “Zhiqing Jiashu” 知青家書 [Family letters from educated youth] accessed through <http://www.hxzq.net/aspshow/showarticle.asp?id=7444>.

Wu, Weiyi and Fan Hong. "The Rise And Fall Of The “Up To The Mountains And Down To The Countryside” Movement: A Historical Review." Accessed through <https://rozenbergquarterly.com/the-rise-and-fall-of-the-up-to-the-mountains-and-down-to-the-countryside-movement-a-historical-review/>.

Wang, Xiaoping. “Fangchuan zhijian tiandi kuan” 方寸之間天地寬 [The world is big in small places]. *Jiancha Fengyun* 4, (2012). Accessed through <https://wenku.baidu.com/view/b45d53174128915f804d2b160b4e767f5bcf806c.html?re=view>.

Appendix

Below are three examples of letters written by Wang Shu in the collection.

All photos are taken by the author.

敬祝毛主席万寿无疆

16

关于姐姐毕业一事，以后安心等待分配。

董林给捐的东两金收到了，请放心。

树

1968年10月25日

20 × 19 = 380

Image 1: The first letter in the collection Wang, Shu, Xiaoshu jiashu. October 5, 1968.

永远忠于伟大领袖毛主席

爸、妈：

你们好！

两次来信均已收到。

此次冯中廉同志回哈去咱家，特捎信回去。

关于我回哈，本应此次一起回去，无奈工作脱身不得；估计我24-25号左右可以起身，26号左右就可以到家。希望文母千万不要着急。

要的东西基本已买好，肥皂、香皂、药皂我都买了，木耳也买了一斤（还没到手）不管怎样，木耳至少也可以带回家去几两。解放胶鞋我们这里没有，手中是可以解决的。至于我的冬季是不成问题的。希望文母不要挂念。

我一定守心工作

1969.5.

Image 2: The second letter in the collection Wang, Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. May, 1969.

敬祝毛主席万寿无疆！

亲爱的爸爸、妈妈、小妹：

你们好！节日快乐

今天是一月二日，已是70年代了！

从家回来已是好几天了，暂时在炊事班工作，爸爸妈妈都知道，赶到节日炊事班很忙，所以拖到今天才给家中写信。

也许这封信很短，现在已经十岁多了！

离开车马班是革命的需要，暂时调到炊事班是革命的需要，只要

有一颗为人民服务的红心，在哪里都一样干好了！

节日的晚上总是忙到很晚，而且很想你们，你们想我吗？

又过了一天，今天是一月三日，小妹过生日好！

妈：我把如何过节说给你们好吗？

节日都不休息，全连战备，但过的很好，包了肉馅饺子，一顿饺子是牛肉，一顿饺子是猪肉是鄂伦春卖给我们的，此外鄂伦春还卖给我们不少狍子肉、野猪肉，总之野味很多，还有鲑鱼一斤、二斤大米

初中我学炒菜，会做馒头了，会做饺子了（这回是真会了，只是慢
点）会捏包子了，这都不是吹牛。

爸：我们现在报纸建议挖地道，可惜土冻的太厉害。但为了诺安
毛泽东同志，奋不顾身，为人民的伟大事业，天不怕，地不怕，每挖
一下就是射向苏联一粒子弹！

上封信中提到的秋秋秋梅已经头好，九十五公分的兰秋秋，100
公分的红秋梅，准备给各女一件、小森一件，我暂时保管，你们商量
一下吧！

在黑河和森森处共蹲了四天，所带的钱全部用光了。回家后开资
又交了上个月的伙食费七元，扣下本月的伙食费，好不容易才凑齐了
买秋秋秋梅的十六元钱，所以下月可能不给家中寄钱了，希望妈
女原谅，据说不同仅给开十九元，这是有可能的！

小妹又长了一岁，快照张像花给大哥，要带相机的。

大哥向什么买的，希望你好好学习。

伊大娘的木耳暂时没买到，会的和木耳控制太紧，呆几天松
了就好了，现在是新年，春节前后卖的较多！

20×16 保存好！ 千万努力！
照快给我寄来！

哈1969.1.3
儿村 一月三十

Image 3: The third letter in the collection Wang, Shu. Xiaoshu jiashu. January 3, 1970.